

ISic3460

Honours for Rubellinus

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Excavated 21 September 2010, in re-use on the decumanus maximus, Capo Boeo

Coordinates

37.802778, 12.429402

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

A thick slab of local, pinkish, limestone; the upper part has a rounded form, consequent upon re-use in antiquity for the covering of a large drain. The surface is extremely worn, especially on the lower and right side of the face.

Dimensions

Height 98 cm

Width 65 cm

Depth 21 cm

Layout

The Latin text fills the preserved face in the upper half at least to both margins, but is extremely worn in the lower parts

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Tall narrow letters, implying a C2-3 AD date

Letter heights:

Lines 1-7: 60-75 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not recorded mm

Text

1. [M(arco)] Rubellino
2. P(ubli) f(ilio) Publ(lilia) Ces[tianotribu]no
3. milit(tum) leg(ionis) [X]X [Val(eriae)Vic(tricis)etleg(ionis)]
4. [X]X[II] Prim[i]g(eniae)[---]
5. p[at]ro[noflam(ini)divor(um)Augg(ustorum)per]p(etuo)
6. IIvir(o) q[u]i[nq]i[(uennali)ite]r[u]m
7. c[ol]i[(oniae) Aug(usta) Lilybitan(orum)]

Apparatus

Text of Silvestrini 2020

Translation

Commentary

Preliminary notice in Silvestrini 2014, full edition in Silvestrini 2020. The same name of Rubellinus is found in ISic0492 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0492>] = CIL 10.7212, now in Mazara del Vallo.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644937

Bibliography

Silvestrini, M. 2014. Nuove epigrafi da Lilibeo. In Zaccaria, C.(eds.), *L'Epigrafia dei porti. Atti della XVIIe recncontre sur l'épigraphie du monde romain, Aquileia, 14-16 ottobre 2010*. Trieste. pp. 207-226. At 209 fig.4

Silvestrini, Marina 2020. Un autorevole tribuno militare e una titolatura imperiale in due epigrafi inedite di Lilibeo. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 213: 294-300. At 294-298 no.1 with figs.1-3

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3460. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358556>

Photo Rebecca Henzel